

Performance Evaluation of MEC-enabled Fiber To The Room Architecture

A. Marotta^{*†}, K. Kondepu[‡], C. Centofanti^{*†}, S. Arnaout^{*},
A. Bhattacharyya[‡], C. Rinaldi[§], F. Graziosi^{*}, D. Cassioli^{*}

^{*} Università Degli Studi Dell'Aquila, L'Aquila, Italy; [†] WEST Aquila S.r.l., L'Aquila, Italy

[‡] Indian Institute of Technology Dharwad, Dharwad, India;

[§] National Inter-university Consortium for Telecommunications (CNIT)

Email: andrea.marotta@univaq.it

Abstract—Modern broadband communications are on the cusp of a transformation, ushered by novel services and augmented by the rise of applications like augmented reality and ultra-HD virtual reality. At the core of this evolution lies the critical role of fixed networks. ETSI's Fifth Generation Fixed Network (F5G) initiative aims to spearhead this change, introducing innovations like the Fibre-to-the-Room (FTTR) concept. Going beyond traditional approaches, FTTR is seen as a key enabler in addressing bottlenecks and interference challenges of WiFi systems. This paper delves into a MEC-enabled FTTR architecture based on dual-stage Passive Optical Networks (PONs), highlighting the potential of FTTR in enabling next-gen services with superior Quality of Service, especially when integrated with edge computing.

Index Terms—FTTR, PON, MEC, Optical Access Networks, DBA, FBA

I. INTRODUCTION

The landscape of modern broadband communications is experiencing a transformative shift, primarily influenced by the introduction and widespread adoption of novel services. These include real-time interactions through high-definition (HD) videos, online gaming platforms that promise immersive experiences, telemedicine applications that are bridging geographical gaps, and online education platforms that democratize access to knowledge globally. As we look to the future, emerging services such as augmented reality (AR), ultra-HD virtual reality (VR), and holographic interactions are setting ambitious new goals for the industry [1]. At the heart of this rapid evolution lies the pivotal role of fixed networks. They act as supporting infrastructure enabling the seamless delivery of these advanced services. Recognizing this, ETSI formed the Industry Specification Group (ISG) initiative for the Fifth Generation Fixed Network (F5G). The primary objective of ISG F5G is to develop a roadmap for this technology generation and expand its application across various sectors through the Fibre-To-The-Everywhere-and-Everything (FTTE) concept. This initiative serves as a platform for synergizing the efforts of other standard development organizations, aligning them towards a unified vision for future fixed networks [2]. One of the key advancements introduced by ETSI ISG F5G is the concept of a fiber connection extending directly to individual rooms, beyond the traditional fiber-to-the-home (FTTH) approach. The new direction focuses on

ensuring a direct fiber connection that reaches individual rooms. Termed as Fibre-to-the-Room (FTTR), this technology promises high-bandwidth and reliable transmission channels, especially if compared to WiFi indoor coverage. The potential of FTTR has also been recognized by ITU-T SG15 Q3, which initiated studies on it in 2020 to explore its applications and set necessary network specifications [3]. Few works in the literature highlight the need for FTTR technology to enable Wi-Fi 7 and beyond coverage avoiding the bottleneck created by the fixed networks within the home and overcoming the impact of APs interference [4]. In [5] a management and control architecture for FTTR back-hauled 5G RAN based on femto cell was proposed showing the capability to offer a wireless data rate up to 800Mbps and latency levels in the order of hundreds of microseconds via dedicated wavelength activation. [1] proposed the integration between Centralized Wireless Access Networks (C-WAN) and FTTR, where the optical infrastructure is utilized to interconnect functional elements composing the WiFi RF-PHY-MAC stack. [6] further explores this direction by proposing a Fiber Wireless Integrated Network (FWIN) exploiting artificial intelligence (AI) accelerated service identification to improve Quality of Service (QoS). In this frame, evaluating the achievable performance of FTTR architecture becomes crucial. In this paper, we analyze an FTTR architecture based on two cascaded Passive Optical Networks (PONs) to bring the FTTR connectivity within the user premise. We delve into the potential of FTTR as a catalyst for next-gen high QoS services by analyzing key performance indicators like latency and jitter. Furthermore, we evaluate the merits of FTTR in conjunction with the exploitation of edge computing deployment.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

The architecture in Fig. 1 shows a Fiber To The Room (FTTR) structure that employs in a first stage a *primary PON* originating from the Central Office (CO) and extends to individual user locations or customer premises. This primary stage configuration usually incorporates multiple 1:N splitting stages, making it suitable to connect with both conventional Optical Network Terminations (ONTs) and client infrastructures possessing a secondary PON. The secondary stage utilizes a PON that is conceived to distribute fiber over

Fig. 1: FTTR architecture.

customer rooms to realize the FTTR infrastructure. This latter network, enabled by a singular splitting phase, efficiently routes the optical fiber to serve between 2-8 ONTs. Such a configuration is ideal for areas like educational campuses, industrial facilities, or multi-unit residential complexes. The primary and secondary PONs are linked at a component termed the *Residential GateWay* (RGW), situated at the customer's location. The GW connects to the primary PON through an ONT interface and functions as an OLT within the secondary PON. Given that PONs typically employ time or wavelength division multiplexing, the RGW collaboratively utilizes optical resources in the primary PON alongside other ONTs to accomplish Dynamic Bandwidth Allocation (DBA). This collaborative use involves multiple access strategies, communicating with the OLT situated in the CO. Conversely, the optical resources within the secondary PON are exclusively dedicated to the devices in that segment. In this domain, the RGW undertakes the duty of distributing resources among the ONTs within the FTTR framework. As shown in Fig. 1, a unified control layer enables end-to-end management of resources including the WiFi segment. In fact, IEEE 802.11be, also known as Wi-Fi7 (and the upcoming Wi-Fi8), stands out as a significant technology for FTTR. It facilitates connections to the FTTR system for mobile devices while concurrently delivering bandwidth capacities (reaching up to 46 Gbps) that align with modern PON systems. The concept of Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) has risen as a compelling model for situating microservices at the network's edge, aiming to offer reduced latency and diminish the traffic load on transport networks. To serve this objective, there have been proposals to equip Central Office (CO) structures with MEC-enabled OLTs [7]. FTTR is intriguing in this context, facilitating the incorporation of MEC at the RGW level (as in Fig. 1). Indeed, operators of industrial campuses are anticipated to construct and oversee their distinct MEC data hubs. Within these elaboration nodes, both computational assets and data

remain restricted to their respective infrastructure environments, ensuring enhanced data segregation. The capability to station service at the RGW, in tandem with overseeing resource allocation within the FTTR, presents an opportunity to cater to services that demand exceptionally low latency and robust bandwidth.

III. FTTR PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

Attainable FTTR performance shape the set of novel services enabled by FTTR. To this extent, we adapt the latency model for E-PONs running IPACT-like dynamic bandwidth allocation strategy [8]. Fig. 2a shows the expected FTTR latency (i.e. ONU to CO) as a function of the load of the secondary PON ρ_2 for different load conditions in the primary PON ρ_1 . In the considered scenario, it is assumed that the OLT at the RGW accomplishes the integrated management and alignment of secondary and primary PON DBAs [9]. Thus, the secondary PON ONUs share and access the optical resources competing with the primary PON ONUs. In fact, results show that ρ_1 and ρ_2 contribute equally to the saturation of the PON where delay goes up to hundreds of ms. In particular, it can be noticed that the FTTR latency reaches 1ms with a load equal to 0.16 when the primary PON is highly loaded ($\rho_1 = 0.75$) and 0.66 when the load in the primary PON is lower ($\rho_1 = 0.25$). Finally, by considering the absent primary PON load, the FTTR is able to guarantee ≤ 1 ms latency up to $\rho_2 = 0.90$. As described in Sec. II, FTTR represents an interesting playground for MEC, since a MEC node can be deployed at the RGW offering low latency to secondary PON ONUs and relying on the entire capacity of the secondary PON. This solution also guarantees high data isolation since it allows to terminate the traffic inside the customer premises. Fig. 2b shows the secondary PON, i.e. the latency between the FTTR ONU and the RGW where the edge instance is placed, for different upstream capacities (1G, 10G, and forthcoming 100G-EPON). It can be noticed that high capacity 10G and

Fig. 2: FTTR latency performance

100G-EPON allow keeping the latency below a hundred of μs making FTTR a suitable solution for extremely low-latency services like tactile internet and critical e-health (e.g. connected surgery). Furthermore, as illustrated in Fig. 2c, it can be noticed that varying the distance between the RGW and the ONU in the secondary PON does not significantly impact the experienced ONU to RGW latency. Finally, in Fig. 2d we analyze the impact of the traffic to be supported in the FTTR system (corresponding to different average and variance of packet size). This may be particularly relevant in edge deployment scenario since the supported traffic is completely under the control of the customer. Hence, the secondary PON can be utilized to support significantly different applications and traffic, for example, industrial automation in productive plants (also known as Guaranteed Reliable Experience(GRE)) or augmented/extended reality in immersive museums (also known as enhanced Fixed BroadBand (eFBB)).As it can be noticed, FTTR in conjunction with MEC deployment at the RGW, while offering good performance for eFBB applications, represents an ideal candidate architecture to support GRE applications since it is able to offer $\leq 10\mu s$ performance in average load conditions.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented a MEC-enabled FTTR architecture and illustrated the challenges and opportunities of FTTR in terms of resource allocation and achievable performance. The analysis we conducted offers valuable insights into the intricacies of resource allocation and latency within the MEC-enabled FTTR architecture. The findings contribute to a better

understanding of the architecture capabilities and limitations, paving the way for its potential application in diverse scenarios, particularly in supporting emerging GRE and eFBB services.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been partially supported by the KDT-JU CLEVER project, SNS-JU SEASON Project (GA:101096120), H2020-MSCA-RISE OPTIMIST project (GA: 872866), and by the Italian Government through projects INCIPICT and VITALITY.

REFERENCES

- [1] X. Wu *et al.*, “Fiber-to-the-room (fttr): Standards and deployments,” in *Optical Fiber Communication Conference 2023*.
- [2] ETSI GR F5G 002 V1.1.1, “Fifth Generation Fixed Network (F5G); F5G Use Cases.”
- [3] ITU-T, “GSTP-FTTR “use cases and requirements of fibre-to-the-room (FTTR)”,” technical Paper.
- [4] T. Chang *et al.*, “Design of dual-polarized beamforming wifi antenna array for fttr applications,” in *2022 International Conference on Microwave and Millimeter Wave Technology (ICMMT)*, 2022, pp. 1–3.
- [5] J. Zhu *et al.*, “First field trial of fttr based on native management and control architecture for 5g small cell backhaul,” in *Optical Fiber Communication Conference (OFC) 2023*, 2023.
- [6] D. Zhang *et al.*, “Fiber-to-the-room: a key technology for f5g and beyond,” *Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 15, no. 9, pp. D1–D9, 2023.
- [7] C. Centofanti *et al.*, “Improved DASH Video Streaming Performance by MEC-Enabled Optical Access,” in *Asia Communications and Photonics Conference 2021*, p. T4A.144.
- [8] J. A. Hernández *et al.*, “Learning epon delay models from data: a machine learning approach,” *Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 13, no. 12, pp. 322–330, 2021.
- [9] F. Effenberger and Y. Luo, “Pon for fiber to the room,” in *2021 Asia Communications and Photonics Conference*.